

Where to find Diamond OA Journals

Diamond OA is a scholarly publication model in which the research output is published open access without applying fees to either authors, readers or their institutions. Diamond OA focuses on academic ownership and it is not for profit. By highlighting ways for finding Diamond OA journals, this flyer aims to promote a model which – while fragmented and (therefore) partly invisible – represents an equitable, diverse and inclusive game changer in the scholarly publishing landscape.

The following resources are listed by geographic scale: worldwide (*DOAJ*), across continents (*Latindex*), continental (*AJOL*, *Diamond Discovery Hub*), country level (*Diamond OA Journals Dashboard*).

You will find: journals worldwide, free of charge for authors, readers, and their institutions; might be controlled by a commercial publisher. **Search** by first refining to 'See journals Without fees'. Then search by Country, journal title, language, license, publisher and/or subject (more: please turn over). [<https://doaj.org/>]

You will find: journals from Latin America, the Caribbean, Spain and Portugal, without fees for authors. **Search** by first choosing 'Publication fees: No' and 'Access type: Open'. Then search by Country, discipline, journal title, language, and/or publisher. [<https://www.latindex.org/latindex/bAvanzada>]

You will find: journals from African Countries, free to download, without fees for authors. **Search** by first refining to 'No fee Open Access'. Then search by Title. Other search options are available, but results can not to be limited to Diamond OA journals only. [<https://www.ajol.info/index.php/ajol/browseBy/Diamond-Open-Access>]

You will find: journals from European Countries. Journals are scholarly, community-owned, open access, free of charge, open to all, and have persistent identification. Combines titles 'Without fees' from DOAJ and additions at Country level, such as 'A curated list of Diamond OA journals in the Netherlands'. **Search** by Country, journal title, language, license, and/or publisher. [<https://ddh.edch.eu/en>]

Diamond OA Journals Dashboard

You will find: journals from The Netherlands, free of charges (for authors, readers, and their institutions), publishing with an open license (e.g. CC BY) immediately upon publication, and controlled by a not-for-profit research community. **Search** by journal title and/or publisher. [<https://www.openaccess.nl/en/resources/diamond-oa-journals-dashboard>]

How to find Diamond OA Journals in a specific research area

As illustrated overleaf, (Diamond) OA resources only partly allow to search for journals or articles on a given topic. Therefore, here below, the flyer presents the search options of a recommender system (*BISON*) and a bibliographic database (*Open Alex*): both allows to find journals (or articles) in a specific research area

BISON

BISON is based on bibliographic information from DOAJ and references from the citation database [OpenCitations](#).

By entering the details of your manuscript (title, abstract, references), you will find a selection of suitable Open Access journals to publish with. Refine results by 'APC: 0 €' for Diamond OA. [<https://service.tib.eu/bison/>]

Open Alex

To search for Diamond OA journals on a given topic, you first search for **articles** (=‘works’). Then refine the results to Diamond OA journals (filter by ‘Open Access Status’ > Diamond).

While Open Alex allows to search for **journals** on a given topic, the results can not be limited to Diamond OA journals only.

[<https://openalex.org/>]